

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Adult Education for Sustainable Learning

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is transforming the teaching and learning process by reshaping andragogical approaches in education. This paper examined how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is promoting adult learning by assisting adult educators and improving adult learner's engagement in education. The paper discussed personalized learning, intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading and feedback, enhanced teacher support, inclusive education as well as ethical concerns about AI. The paper relied on qualitative data from books, journals, e-books and other online resources. Based on discussions, it was recommended that collaborations between adult educators, policy makers and technologists are essential to harnessing the potentials of AI.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, adult education, sustainable learning.

Introduction

Education has experienced a digital transformation since the last decade which is significant in adult education. Presently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionised such that it is now playing major roles across different contexts in education. For instance, it is used to reduce administrative burden for educators and is used by adult learners in tackling learning tasks thus, AI tools are now maximized when adults are learning to promote their learning experiences. These advancement has made AI a valuable asset along traditional and online learning processes.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) was designed to help computers and machines to think like humans; to process thoughts, understand things, have an opinion and make suggestions as well as solve problems thus, resembling human cognitive abilities. AI applications include tasks like object recognition, speech understanding, and language translation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is conceived as computers and machines having the power to do what humans can do. IBM (2014) describes AI a new craft, that gives machines the power of intelligence, to think like humans by regularly re developing and upgrading their designs and their information through knowledge acquisition, reasoning, and handling responsibilities. Although AI has gained recent popularity, its origins trace back to Alan Turing's work during World War II (Turing, 1950). Turing's imitation game set the foundation for this new invention as we can see in applications like chatbots, ChatGPT etc. The application is designed such that it is able to make decisions for itself based on information it receives which in this stance has been stored over a long period of time and; programmed to carry out these tasks. Although a robot or computer is limited it stores data and what it has been programmed or trained to do. AI has gained so much popularity, the concept is far older than we can imagine. The origins of AI can be traced as far back as World War II (WWII) by Alan Turing who broke the enigma code during that war. He devised a test in 1950 which laid the premise where other apps were launched like chatbox and now chatGPT. Tasks that will take time to be done is now done within seconds with the help of AI which goes as far as performing tasks like medical screenings. Currently, most users of this new craft maximize the generative AI. How does this work? Since AI is already trained to simulate human intelligence, reason, take decisions etc and has

been fed a large quantity of resource (programmed information which it has been fed overtime), asking it to generate information or giving it a task to perform for you is what generative AI is all about. This is what most users do with the chatGPT app. Using the chatGPT app is simple. Once the app is downloaded and opened, the user is asked by the AI what he will like the AI to do for him. A prompt is popped up for the user so he or she can request the AI to perform any task of his choice. This can be just about anything and cuts across disciplines. Within seconds, answers to questions, resource on any topic, speeches, research findings, formats, images, templates etc based on the user's needs is generated by the AI for the user. This ease of access and use can improve adult education.

How Artificial Intelligence is helping Adult Educators and adult learners in the process of Teaching and Learning.

AI has created a major shift with respect to how adult educators and learners usually receive or process information. As professionals in the field, they usually prepare teaching materials and contents after personally gathering and examining a large volume of resources from different sources from the library like books, journals, texts, online resources, e books, e-libraries etc however, with AI, resources from all these avenues are brought to the Educator's doorstep all at once with sometimes a preview of what it should look like in real life; taking away the painstaking task of sorting and mentally processing data in an organized, logical and coherent manner. The same is for the adult learners who barely has time to meet up the demands of adult life and daily task who finds himself in a formal, informal or non-formal learning activity. In the same vein, AI can generate any learning resource required making it easy for him and saving him time and resources. AI is contributing to teaching and learning in the following ways:

Promoting Self-directed Learning

UNESCO (2017), emphasizes that education should meet the learner on a personal level. This means that for the learning process to be impactful, it must be something the learner wants and needs for his personal development. Since most adult learners decide what and when to learn, AI has become critical not only in promoting self-directed learning but making the process easier since it brings the required knowledge to the doorstep of the adult learner thus satisfying their educational needs. This has further eased the burden of educators in the field as well as major stakeholders who emphasise the need of satisfying the learner's needs. AI systems like Carnegie Learning adjust content difficulties based on performance (Ritter et al., 2007) improving outcomes by 30% (Pane et al., 2017) and use machine learning algorithms to adjust difficulty levels based on student performance, ensuring optimal learning progression. Studies show that personalized learning powered by AI improves student outcomes by up to 30% compared to traditional methods (Pane et al., 2017).

Automated Grading and Feedback

AI helps adult educators by providing access to tools that makes grading and assessing learners easy. AI-driven tools like Gradescope achieve accuracy comparable to human graders while Turnitin (Wahid et al., 2020) avails adult educators with automated grading for multiple-choice and even essay-based assessments, saving educators time while providing students with instant feedback. A study by Shermis and Hamner (2013) found that AI grading systems reach accuracy levels comparable to human graders, particularly in structured assessments.

Intelligent Tutoring Systems

Tutoring adult learners is no longer limited to adult educators. There are AI controlled platforms which are interactive that can help tutor adult learners. Information Technology Service (ITS) such

as Squirrel and IBM Watson Tutor (Kose & Arslan, 2019), provide one-on-one tutoring by analyzing student responses and offering customized explanations. These systems mimic human tutors, improving comprehension and retention. Research indicates that students using ITS perform 10-20% better on assessments than those in conventional learning settings (VanLehn, 2011).

Providing Support for Adult Educators and Facilitators

AI assists adult educators by generating lesson plans, identifying learning gaps, and recommending interventions. Virtual teaching assistants, such as Jill Watson at Georgia Tech, assist students with higher-level instructions and tutors to track student progress and adjusting instructions accordingly.

Inclusive Education

AI supports adult learners with disabilities through predictive analytics that identify at-risk learners (Baker & Inventado, 2014). These technologies ensure equitable access to education for diverse learners.

Adult Education and Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Learning

Adult education is the education that embraces the formal, informal and non-formal types of education. It is a process and an agent of liberation which is perceived differently and defined as one see fit based on his culture and environment. It is also a process whereby adults who no longer attend schooling, dropped out of school, or who require a second chance are given an opportunity to acquire knowledge, skill, values and attitudes through formal, informal and non-formal processes of learning. It is an all-inclusive process which promotes lifelong learning for adults in society so they can re learn, unlearn, reskill or upskill for efficiency and productivity. To keep the adults in society educated, not obsolete in knowledge and abreast with technological changes and current trends, is no mean feat. There is therefore a strong need to maximize the support of AI which offers several opportunities for adult learners to maximize, making the process of teaching and learning easier and less time consuming. While it is important to maximize the opportunities of AI, it is important to retain the aspect of stimulating and arousing student's interest to seek knowledge for themselves and to arrive at new findings; to uphold and sustain educational values and principles which are key to preserving knowledge. Sustainability means having the ability to meet our own needs such that we do not destroy avenues or opportunities for the generations behind us to do same for themselves. This means that the use of AI should not water down the teaching and learning processes for educators and learners such that Educators will lose their originality and teaching skills while students become mentally lazy, cannot think for themselves, no longer seek knowledge or loose the desire and need to learn thus, the need to emphasize sustainability in learning. Sustainable learning has to do with teaching learners so that they can acquire knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes required to shape a sustainable future that will last (UNESCO, 2019). The purpose and emphasis about sustainability here, is to help learners understand the complex relationships between the environment, economy, and society, as well as recognize the importance of sustainability and its impact on their lives. This in essence is to help learners make informed decisions and take action to address global issues which AI should promote and not demote.

Moralities to uphold and Difficulties Experienced by Adult Educators and Adult Learners in the Use of AI.

The use of AI raises ethical questions about data usage, consent, and the potential for manipulation. For example, AI systems can be used to target individuals with personalized advertising or to influence their behavior. This goes contrary to regulations like the NDPR and GDPR. The NDPR (Nigerian Data Protection Regulation) is a general protection law that restricts access to the data of Nigerians. GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) is a European Union law that controls how

personal data of EU citizens is collected and processed, regardless of where the processing takes place. Although the value and benefits of AI in education is far reaching. AI offers educators and adult learners several opportunities that has improved teaching and learning. Irrespective of these, there are challenges educators and learners are facing with the use of AI. These challenges include: Data Privacy: Data privacy is a significant concern with AI because AI systems, particularly those powered by machine learning, depend on a lot of collected and stored data which is studied and maximized to make projections. This increases the risk of unauthorized access, misuse, and potential breaches. Data privacy issues include:

Data Collection and Usage: Most learners in maximizing resource provided by AI can make the data collected theirs without properly recognizing the true authors even when these authors are cited by AI. AI systems require vast datasets to train their models. This includes personal information like names, addresses, financial records, and even medical history. Without proper safeguards, this data can be misused or exposed, leading to identity theft, fraud, or other privacy violations. (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights [FRA], 2020).

Bias and Discrimination: Discrimination may arise in AI use. Since AI make projections based on algorithms, if there were biases contained in the already collected data, it can further result in biases when hiring, lending, or even in criminal justice.

Lack of Transparency and Accountability: The nature of many AI algorithms makes it difficult to understand how decisions are made. This lack of transparency raises questions about accountability and fairness, especially when AI systems are used in high-stakes situations. (Burrell, 2016).

Unintentional Data Leaks: While AI is often used for tasks like pattern detection and anomaly detection, it can also inadvertently identify sensitive information or patterns in datasets, leading to unintended data leaks.

Unequal Access to AI tools: Everyone who intends to maximise AI tools cannot do so, it will create a knowledge gap which goes contrary to the Sustainable Development Goals (2017). Residents in developing countries who cannot afford digital devices like computers and who cannot pay for trainings to learn how to use AI tools will be denied access and cannot maximize the opportunities offered by AI. Furthermore, the challenge of paying monthly subscription for these tools like Canva, Adobe Express, VistaCreate etc are bills that most residents cannot afford since most can barely afford the basic necessities of life.

Conclusion

Collaboration between educators, policymakers, and technologists has become essential to harness the full potential of AI responsibly. Artificial Intelligence is a powerful tool that can help Adult educators to promote sustainable learning if properly maximised. To fully realise its potentials, the Government, policy makers, educational institutions, instructors, curriculum designers, researchers and educational technology providers must collaborate to plan, set parameters for the use of AI as well as adopt it in learning to promote ease of access for adult learners.

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